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**HISTORY OF RESIDENTIAL COMPLEXES IN THE CITY OF TASHKENT AND
MODERN TRENDS IN THEIR DESIGN**

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Abstract: This article examines the history of residential complexes in Tashkent, covering several stages, each reflecting various socioeconomic and architectural processes occurring in the city and current trends in residential complex design, reflecting changing demands on the urban environment and social needs. Particular attention is paid to key aspects such as the flexibility and adaptability of spaces, environmental sustainability, the integration of high technologies, and social and public integration. It concludes that modern residential complexes strive to create a sustainable and comfortable urban environment capable of adapting to change and meeting the needs of residents.

Keywords: city, residential areas, residential complex, sustainable architecture, autonomous architecture, adaptive architecture, living environment, residential buildings.

In recent decades, mass residential development has significantly expanded in the cities of Uzbekistan, resulting in the emergence of a new mass-produced architecture that is sharply different from traditional architecture. This architecture is not immune to the general complex challenges of contemporary mass architecture. As in other republics of the country, the architectural and artistic expressiveness of residential development and its uniqueness are becoming pressing issues in urban development in Uzbekistan.

Creating a distinctive mass-produced architecture has proven to be a complex challenge, requiring a creative approach to the principles and techniques of traditional residential architecture, taking into account the complexities of the population's lifestyle, climate, aesthetic needs, and a number of key urban planning objectives.

The above-mentioned challenges in the development of residential zones in large

and major cities of Uzbekistan are inextricably interrelated. This interrelationship is particularly acute in the current stage of urban development. It is at the intersection of the interrelationships between social, architectural, urban planning, economic, and other aspects of the formation of urban residential zones that new, effective, and promising directions for its development are born.

As cities grow, the practice of strictly zoning residential, industrial, and commercial zones is losing its relevance. This leads to uneven development and increased pressure on transportation systems. Contemporary socioeconomic changes have necessitated a reconsideration of approaches to the organization of residential areas. In response to these challenges, urban planning requires improving the organization of the urban environment, ensuring more efficient use of space, and creating closer connections between public and residential areas.

In Soviet cities, residential planning was based on zoning structured according to the principles of multi-level distribution and a unified KBO system. Over time, this model led to the formation of two large spatial segments: the central business zone and peripheral residential areas. The business center, a complex multifunctional structure, gradually lost its vitality, and the microdistricts began to experience various social difficulties. Tashkent is one of the largest and oldest cities in Central Asia, which, since ancient times, has been an important economic, cultural, and administrative center of the region. The history of residential complexes in Tashkent has passed through several stages, each reflecting the various socioeconomic and architectural processes taking place in the city.

Tashkent as a city has over two thousand years of history, and its architectural heritage is linked to periods of diverse cultural influences. In ancient and medieval times, cities were built as fortified settlements with organic layouts, where housing consisted of compact houses and courtyards, often combined into small complexes. Numerous madrassas, temples, shopping arcades, and merchant houses were part of ancient Tashkent, but the concept of a "residential complex" in its modern sense did not yet exist at that time.

Residential spaces were typically small and often arranged around courtyards, forming small micro-districts. A notable feature was the use of the courtyard as a shared space for family needs, a characteristic feature of the traditional Eastern dwelling. Since 1865, when Tashkent became part of the Russian Empire, its active urbanization and integration into the Russian economy and infrastructure began. At this time, the first apartment buildings began to be constructed, although most housing remained one- or two-story, consisting of a few rooms and courtyards.

At this time, the process of creating new residential neighborhoods with elements of Western architecture began. One of the first examples was the construction boom at the beginning of the 20th century, when Tashkent began to develop one- and two-story

houses with improved layouts. An important aspect of this period was the creation of the first communal apartments and apartment buildings, aimed at the needs of the urban elite. With the advent of Soviet power in the 1920s, Tashkent experienced significant changes, both socially and architecturally. Industrialization began, along with active construction, including residential developments.

From the 1930s to the 1950s, Tashkent saw the development of mass-produced residential neighborhoods for workers. This period was characterized by the construction of so-called "standard residential buildings," among which the distinctive "Khrushchev-era" buildings—five- and nine-story residential buildings with simple layouts and limited amenities—were prominent. These residential buildings were characterized by functionality, but often at the expense of aesthetics and comfort.

Since the 1950s, large-scale construction of residential complexes has begun in Tashkent as part of a program to improve housing for urban residents. The construction of multi-story residential buildings in Tashkent became popular, and the development of new housing stock proceeded rapidly. By this time, new architectural styles, including elements of modernism, had emerged. More modern residential complexes with convenient layouts, new utility systems, and landscaped courtyards appeared in the city. This period can be considered the period of development of large residential complexes, such as those in the southern part of the city (for example, the Mirabad, Chilanzar, and other microdistricts).

In the 1980s and 1990s, the first multi-level residential complexes with improved layouts emerged. Interest in housing quality continued to grow, and new residential complexes began to include additional features, such as underground parking and modern facades. In the final years of the USSR, residential construction in Tashkent became more diverse, incorporating new technologies and building materials.

After Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, Tashkent began to change rapidly. Residential development in the city continued, but with new emphasis, including individualization and improving quality of life. In the 1990s and 2000s, the city continued to develop apartment buildings and microdistricts. However, amid the country's economic difficulties during this period, Tashkent faced challenges in providing affordable housing. At the same time, more modern residential complexes, aimed at the upper class, began to be built, featuring additional amenities such as swimming pools, fitness centers, and gated communities.

Since the early 2000s, active development of luxury residential complexes and modern residential complexes with business features has begun. The construction of multi-level residential complexes with developed internal infrastructure, such as shopping and entertainment centers, banks, and other amenities, has become increasingly popular. At this time, projects for residential complexes integrated with natural landscapes, such as complexes with parks and landscaping, began. Tashkent continues to develop rapidly, and in recent years, numerous new residential projects

have been implemented in the city, including multifunctional residential complexes with improved utility systems, projects for young people, luxury residential complexes, and luxury residential complexes. Both high-rise residential buildings and compact residential complexes with developed social and utility infrastructure are being built.

Today, the city of Tashkent is actively developing a new image for its urban residential complexes. Many new residential complexes are designed with modern quality and environmental standards in mind, including energy efficiency, the use of eco-friendly materials, and smart home systems. The focus is on innovative solutions such as comprehensive landscaping, integration with public spaces, and the creation of a comfortable environment for living, working, and relaxing.

Thus, the history of residential complexes in Tashkent reflects not only the city's socioeconomic transformations but also the evolution of approaches to the architecture and planning of residential neighborhoods. From traditional houses and fortified settlements in ancient times to modern multifunctional residential complexes, the city continues to adapt to the changing needs of its population.

Modern trends in residential complex design: Over time, people's needs and spatial requirements change, necessitating the transformation of architectural solutions in line with current social trends. This has led to the development of adaptive, flexible, and multifunctional architecture. Instead of designing rooms with a specific function, architects are increasingly creating spaces that can serve a variety of purposes. This explains the popularity of solutions like open kitchens or modular designs that allow for a hybrid lifestyle.

Flexibility and adaptability

Environmental sustainability

Technology integration

Fig. 1. Modern trends in the design of residential complexes.

Modern homes often include bedrooms that can be used as home offices, bathrooms combined with laundry rooms, or kitchens that double as dining rooms. Unlike traditional homes with rigid layouts that limit the use of space, hybrid buildings are able to accommodate multiple functions related to both work and leisure.

In the 21st century, sustainable development and eco-friendly, high-tech architecture have become key design trends.

This strategy aims to improve quality of life and address pressing issues such as environmental change, an aging society, employment, and food shortages. Sustainable architecture incorporates various aspects, adapting to natural, climatic, and technological conditions, combining stable and changing elements in designed structures. An important aspect is adaptability to natural conditions and the use of mathematical modeling to design buildings, taking into account factors that influence their durability and functionality.

Thus, the most notable trends in the design of residential complexes are flexibility and adaptability, environmental sustainability, technological integration, and social and community integration (Fig. 1).

Other contemporary trends in development also stand out:

- The integration of business functions into the residential environment, creating a diversity of spaces and functions (polycentricity).
- Ensuring local functional diversity and accessibility of all necessary services, as well as the development of energy-efficient and autonomous systems (autonomy).
- Defining and clearly delineating the areas of responsibility of various residential units, which is especially relevant in complex multifunctional complexes (boundary regulation).

- Increasing the use of courtyard spaces to meet the needs of people of different age groups (intensification of courtyard spaces).
- Creating an open and accessible complex of spaces for all residents (the concept of openness and transparency).

Conclusion: The developed principles for organizing the functional planning structure of urban residential zones, based on the formation of qualitatively new types of "residential complexes," are the result of the development of general principles laid down in traditional microdistricts and residential areas, taking into account a comprehensive and effective solution to the republic's pressing urban development problems.

They specifically illustrate the effectiveness of this approach to improving the planning structure of urban residential zones; they allow for the consideration of the specific features of individual urban development situations and construction areas, the consolidation and coordination of everyday and periodic use facilities within a single center, significantly increasing the intensity of land use, and improving the architectural and artistic appearance and spatial design of residential development in the cities of Uzbekistan. The study identified contemporary trends in the design of multifunctional residential complexes, including flexibility and adaptability, environmental sustainability, technological integration, social and community integration, political centrality, autonomy, boundary regulation, intensification of courtyard spaces, and openness and transparency.

These identified trends suggest that today's multifunctional residential complexes strive to create a more sustainable and comfortable urban environment, capable of adapting to changing conditions and residents' needs. These principles not only improve quality of life but also contribute to more equitable urban development, improved social structure, and more efficient use of urban spaces.

REFERENCES:

1. Mukhamedzhanov, K.Kh. Formation of the architectural planning structure of residential areas and microdistricts (using large and major cities of Uzbekistan as an example). Volume 1. Dissertation and author's abstract, according to the Higher Attestation Commission of the Russian Federation, 18.00.04.
2. Ryabova M.G. Evolution of a multifunctional residential building complex as an

- urban development unit // Construction and technogenic safety. Simferopol: KFU im. V.I. Vernadsky, 2014. Pp. 35-39.
3. Iconographer O.G. Modern approaches to the design of multifunctional residential complexes in final qualifying works on architectural specialties // University complex as a regional center of education, science and culture. Orenburg: OSU, 2016. Pp. 532-538.
 4. Solodilova L.A., Trukhacheva G.A. Multifunctional residential complex. Moscow: Publishing house of the Association of construction universities, 2009. 153 p.
 5. Alekseev S.Yu., Mironov E.I. The structure of the space of a residential building. Evolution of ideas. Rostov-on-Don: RAI, 1995. 57 p.
 6. [Ecological Problems of Public Spaces in a Modern City Center](#)
S Guljazira, S Oripova, Z Polotova... - E3S Web of Conferences, 2024
 7. Fedyeva N.A. Multifunctional residential complexes. Moscow: MArchI, 1981. 122 p.
 8. [Status of Locals in the Development of Citie of Uzbekistan](#) SG Adilbaevna - International Journal on Orange Technologies